

Advantages of Metformin Therapy for Diabetic Foot Ulcer Prevention and Mitigation

Ahmed Ata Alsubayti¹, Khaled Mohammed Arafah², Raghdaa Khaled Alhmaid³, Amal Saad Alanzi⁴, Saeed Yahya Saeed⁵, Fahad Jazi Albogami⁶, Safar Mohammad Almutairi⁷, Thamer Ali Sehmi Alshomrani⁸

^{1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8}Ministry of Health, Saudi Arabia

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Diabetes foot is one of the most common complications of diabetes. Metformin treatment may aid in lowering the prevalence of diabetic foot ulcers in diabetic patients.

Study objectives: The purpose of this study was to look into the prevalence of diabetic foot ulcers among diabetic patients attending out-patient, as well as the impact of metformin treatment on the development of diabetic foot ulcers.

Methodology: To collect data from diabetic patients' files, a retrospective design was used. Demographic variables such as gender and age were included in the study, as well as clinical variables such as diabetes duration, metformin treatment, and diabetic foot ulcer status. Data was gathered and entered into SPSS version 20 for analysis. Descriptive features of statistical analysis included frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. Various statistical models, such as the Chi-square test, One Way Anova, and Pearson's correlation, were used to investigate the relationship between variables. If $p < 0.05$, the significance was accepted.

Results: The study included 62 diabetic patients with an average age of 56.9511.98 years. The males were 33 (53.2%), the duration of diabetes was 7.55.86 years, metformin was prescribed to approximately 66% of patients, the mean metformin dose was 1617.32649.49 mg, and the prevalence of DF was 8.1%. There were no significant relationships between DF and gender or metformin use ($p > 0.05$). Both the One-Way Anova Test and the correlation test revealed that DF was significantly related to DF.

Conclusion: The current study found that metformin treatment is significantly associated with metformin dose and could protect diabetic patients from developing DF.

KEYWORDS: Diabetic foot (DF), Diabetes, Metformin, Ulcer.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
19 November 2022

Available on:
<https://ijpbms.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a group of metabolic diseases characterized by hyperglycemia and abnormal lipid metabolism, carbohydrates, and insulin resistance, and it is the leading cause of death in the world for noncommunicable diseases¹. Epidemiological studies revealed that approximately 382 million people worldwide were diagnosed with diabetes in 2013, with the number expected to rise to 592 million cases by 2020. worldwide². Diabetes is associated with a number of complications, including cardiovascular problems, vascular insufficiency, renal damage, retinopathy, and diabetic foot (DF). Diabetic patients' quality of life suffers as a result of these complications³ and healthcare systems are

overburdened⁴⁻⁷.

DF is regarded as one of the most serious diabetic complications, with significant financial and quality-of-life consequences. At the global level, DF is the leading cause of non-traumatic amputation^{4, 8}. The global prevalence of DF has been estimated to range between 4.4 and 10.5%⁹.

Diabetic foot lesions are a complicated matter that requires the presence of three factors: neuropathy, peripheral vascular disease, and infection¹⁰⁻¹¹.

Several studies have found that metformin reduces the risks of microvascular and macrovascular disease by lowering weight gain and hyperinsulinemia, improving endothelial function and fibrinolysis, and decreasing low-grade

Advantages of Metformin Therapy for Diabetic Foot Ulcer Prevention and Mitigation

inflammation, oxidative stress, and glycation¹²⁻¹⁴.

Diabetes patients are more likely to require insulin treatment¹⁵. However, other studies in insulin-treated diabetic patients have shown that metformin has the potential to improve glycemic control, reduce insulin needs, and reduce weight gain¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

STUDY OBJECTIVES

To look into the prevalence of diabetic foot ulcers among diabetic patients who come to Medical Services for out-of-hours care, as well as the role of metformin treatment in the development of diabetic foot ulcers.

METHODOLOGY

A retrospective design was used to collect data from diabetic patients' files. The study sample included 62 diabetic patient files. Demographic variables such as gender and age were included in the study, as well as clinical variables such as

diabetes duration, metformin treatment, and diabetic foot ulcer status. Data was gathered and entered into SPSS version 20 for analysis. Descriptive features of statistical analysis included frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. Various statistical models, such as the Chi-Square test, One Way Anova, and Pearson's correlation, were used to investigate the relationship between variables. If $p < 0.05$, the significance was accepted.

RESULTS

Characteristics of Study Participants

The study included 62 diabetic patients, according to the data in table (1). The average age was $56.95 \pm 11.98\%$. Males were found to be 33 (53.2%) of the time (Figure 1); the duration of diabetes was 7.5 ± 5.86 years; metformin use was documented in approximately 66% of diabetic patients (Figure 2); the mean metformin dose was 1617.32 ± 649.49 mg, and the prevalence of DF was 8.1%. (Figure 3).

Table 1. Characteristics of study participants

Variable	Description
Age (M+SD) years	56.95+11.98
Gender (N, %):	
- Males	33 (53.2%)
- Females	29 (46.8%)
Duration of diabetes (M+SD) years	7.5+5.86
Metformin use (N, %):	
- Yes	41 (66.1%)
- No	21 (33.9%)
Metformin dose (M+SD) mg	1617.32+649.49
Diabetic foot (N, %):	
- Yes	5 (8.1%)
- No	57 (91.9%)

Figure 1: Frequency of diabetic patients by gender

Advantages of Metformin Therapy for Diabetic Foot Ulcer Prevention and Mitigation

Figure 2: Frequency of diabetic patients by metformin use

Figure 3. frequency of diabetic foot by diabetic patients

The Relationship Between DF and Study Variables

The Chi-Square test was used to examine the relationship between diabetic DF and study variables. The relationship between DF and gender was not statistically significant

($p=0.658$). The relationship between DF and metformin use was also investigated, but it was not statistically significant ($p=0.157$). Metformin was prescribed to all diabetic patients who developed DF, according to a trend (table 2).

Table 2. The relationship between diabetic foot and study variables (based on Chi-Square test)

Variable	DF				P value
	Yes		No		
	N	%	N	%	
Gender:					0.658
- Males	2	6.1	31	93.9	
- Females	3	10.3	26	89.7	
Metformin use:					0.157
- Yes	5	12.2	36	87.8	
- No	0	0	21	100	

Predictors of DF from Study Variables

The One-Way Anova Test was used to determine the

predictors of DF from study variables. Table 3 shows that there was no significant relationship between DF and any of

Advantages of Metformin Therapy for Diabetic Foot Ulcer Prevention and Mitigation

the study variables ($p>0.05$), with the exception of metformin dose, which was significantly associated with DF ($p=0.05$).

Table 3. Predictors of DF from study variables

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Age	Between Groups	8.476	1	8.476	0.058	0.810
	Within Groups	8740.379	60	145.673		
	Total	8748.855	61			
Gender	Between Groups	.095	1	.095	0.372	0.544
	Within Groups	15.340	60	.256		
	Total	15.435	61			
Duration	Between Groups	100.183	1	100.183	3.013	0.088
	Within Groups	1995.063	60	33.251		
	Total	2095.246	61			
Metformin use	Between Groups	.624	1	.624	2.823	0.098
	Within Groups	13.263	60	.221		
	Total	13.887	61			
Metformin dose	Between Groups	1829015.134	1	1829015.134	4.085	0.050
	Within Groups	17463789.744	39	447789.481		
	Total	19292804.878	40			

Correlation between study variables

When the study variables were correlated, the only significant correlation was found between DF and metformin dose ($p=0.308$).

Table 4. Correlation between DF and study variables

Variable		DF	Age	Gender	Duration	Metformin use	Metformin dose
DF	Pearson Correlation	1	0.031	0.079	0.219	0.212	0.308
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.810	0.544	0.088	0.098	0.050
	N	62	62	62	62	62	41

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to determine the prevalence of DF in diabetic patients and to look into the role of metformin treatment in the development of diabetic foot ulcers.

According to the findings of this study, the prevalence of DF was 8.1%. This finding is consistent with other studies that found DF prevalence ranging from 4.4 to 10.5%⁹. Due to the fact that diabetes is becoming more common over time, as well as the effects of DF on economic and quality of life^{4, 8}, Controlling diabetes is critical for mitigating these effects.

The findings of this study revealed that DF was significantly related to metformin dose ($p=0.05$). This finding is consistent with other published studies. These studies focused on the mechanisms by which metformin reduces the risks of microvascular and macrovascular disease, such as lowering weight gain and hyperinsulinemia, improving endothelial

function and fibrinolysis, and lowering low-grade inflammation, oxidative stress, and glycation¹²⁻¹⁴.

Other studies have shown that metformin treatment can improve glycemic control, reduce insulin needs, and reduce weight gain¹⁶⁻¹⁸

CONCLUSIONS

The current study found that metformin treatment is significantly associated with metformin dose and may help diabetic patients avoid developing DF.

REFERENCES

- I. Park J, Peters PA. Mortality from diabetes mellitus, 2004 to 2008: A multiple-cause-of-
- II. death analysis. Health Rep., 2014, 25(3):12–6.
- III. Guariguata L, Whiting DR, Hambleton I, Beagley J,

Advantages of Metformin Therapy for Diabetic Foot Ulcer Prevention and Mitigation

- Linnenkamp U, Shaw JE. Global estimates of diabetes prevalence for 2013 and projections for 2035. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.*,2014, 103(2):137–49.
- IV. Lee WJ, Song KH, Noh JH, Choi YJ, Jo MW. Health-related quality of life using the EuroQol 5D questionnaire in Korean patients with type 2 diabetes. *J Korean Med Sci.*, 2012, 27(3):255–60.
- V. Rodriguez Bolanos Rde L, ReynalesShigematsu LM, Jimenez Ruiz JA, Juarez Marquezy SA, Hernandez Avila M. Direct costs of medical care for patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus in Mexico micro-costing analysis. *Rev PanamSaludPublica.*, 2010, 28(6):412–20.
- VI. O'Reilly DJ, Xie F, Pullenayegum E, Gerstein HC, Greb J, Blackhouse GK, et al. Estimation of the impact of diabetes-related complications on health utilities for patients with type 2 diabetes in Ontario, Metformin and Wound Healing in Diabetic Foot Ulcers. *Life Res.*, 2011, 20(6):939–43.
- VII. Castro-Rios A, Nevarez-Sida A, Tiro- Sanchez MT, Wachter-Rodarte N. Triggering factors of primary care costs in the years following type 2 diabetes diagnosis in Mexico. *Arch Med Res.*,2014, 45(5):400–8.
- VIII. Ng CS, Lee JY, Toh MP, Ko Y. Cost-of- illness studies of diabetes mellitus: a systematic review. *Diabetes Res ClinPract.*, 2014, 105(2):151–63.
- IX. Margolis DJ, Jeffcoate W. Epidemiology of foot ulceration and amputation: can global variation be explained? *Med Clin North Am.*2013, 97(5):791–805.
- X. Singh N, Armstrong DG, Lipsky BA. Preventing foot ulcers in patients with diabetes. *JAMA.*2005, 293 (2):217–28.
- XI. Murphie P. Macrovascular disease aetiology and diabetic foot ulceration. *J Wound Care*, 2001, 10 (4):103-107.
- XII. Krishnan STM, Baker NR, Carrington AL, Raymann G. Comparative roles of microvascular and nerve function in foot ulceration in type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care*, 2004, 27(6):1343-1348.
- XIII. Beisswenger PJ, Howell SK, Touchette AD, Lal S, Swerzgold BS. Metformin reduces systemic methylglyoxal levels in type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes*, 1999, 48(1): 198-202.
- XIV. Kirpichnikov D, McFarlane SI, Sowers JR Metformin: an update. *Ann Intern Med*, 2002, 137 (1):25-33.
- XV. De Jager J, Kooy A, Lehert P, et al . Effects of short-term treatment with metformin on markers of endothelial function and inflammatory activity in type 2 diabetes mellitus: a randomised, placebo-controlled trial. *J Intern Med*, 2005, 257(1):100-109.
- XVI. Marre M. Before oral agents fail: the case for starting insulin early. *Int J ObesRelatMetabDisord.*, 2002, 26(3):25-30.
- XVII. Avile's-Santa L, Sinding J, Raskin P. Effects of metformin in patients with poorly controlled insulin-treated type 2 diabetes mellitus: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Ann Intern Med.*,1999, 131(3):182-188.
- XVIII. Yki-Järvinen H, Ryysy L, Nikkilä K, Tulokas T, Vanamo R, Heikkilä M. Comparison of bedtime insulin regimens in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus: a randomized, controlled trial. *Ann Intern Med.*, 1999, 130 (5):389-396.
- XIX. Wulffele' MG, Kooy A, Lehert P, et al. Combination of insulin and metformin in the treatment of type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care.*, 2002, 25(12):2133-2140.